

FABRICATION BY TAPE CASTING AND HOT PRESSING OF COPPER DIAMOND COMPOSITE FILMS

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1. Introduction

Thermal management in power electronic devices has reached critical importance because of the constant rise of both power and chip density in integrated circuits (ICs). Currents semiconductor materials showing extreme efficiencies and generating more and more heat (the power density frequently reaches 100 W.cm^{-2}), thermal package design has become one of the major limiting factors for power devices performances and reliability [1-2].

Heat-spreading materials for ICs must have both high thermal conductivity (TC) and low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) to be compatible with chip materials. Former widely spread heat-spreading materials like ceramics such as Al_2O_3 , AlN , Si_3N_4 , or metal-matrix composites such as Cu-W , Cu-Mo , Al-SiC exhibit compatible CTEs with chip materials but their thermal conductivities are becoming too low to remove heat from devices.

Diamond has the highest thermal conductivity at room temperature of all known materials ($\lambda = 1000\text{-}2000 \text{ W.m}^{-1}\text{.K}^{-1}$). However, its very low CTE ($\alpha = 1.10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ at 20 K) is a drawback. The most promising application of diamond is to be used as dispersed particles in a package substrate like a metallic matrix for instance, forming a composite material. This way, the high thermal conductivity of diamond can be associated to the ductile matrix leading to a tailorable CTE for the copper - diamond composite materials [1-2].

We report here the fabrication of diamond dispersed – copper matrix composite films by associating tape casting and hot pressing and the evaluation of their thermal properties.

Tape casting is a well-known process industrially employed to make ceramic layered materials (capacitors). However, the tape casting of metal matrix composites is in its early stages. It consists in prepare a slurry containing copper and diamond

powders mixed with organics, tape it at certain thickness, shape it as desired, and then treat it thermally and mechanically to form a dense material. It shows numerous advantages: good surface finish, thickness control, material net-shaping, large scale capability, and low cost. In addition to the advantages previously mentioned, it also enables to get a uniform dispersion of diamond particles in the copper matrix, which is made complicated by the difference of density between the two materials when using a classical mixing procedure [3-4].

An additional issue when fabricating copper – diamond composites is the very weak chemical affinity between the two materials. The non-reactive copper – diamond interface is critically detrimental to the thermal properties of the composite (degraded thermal conductivity, low load transfer). Carbide forming materials, such as chromium or boron, are usually used to bond diamond reinforcements to the copper matrix. However, these interlayers can affect the thermal properties of the composite by inducing additional thermal boundary resistances [5-6].

We used here an innovative process which consists in deposit copper particles onto diamond reinforcements through C-O-P-O-Cu and/or C-P-O-Cu bonds using thermal treatments prior to sintering in order to create strong chemical bonding between the diamond powder and the copper matrix, as shown in figure 3. This process enables to get, after hot pressing, cohesive and dense copper – diamond composites without any interlayer material, thus optimal thermal properties between Cu and diamond.

The copper - diamond composite films fabricated by the above-described process exhibit very interesting thermal conductivity and CTE and ended be used as heat-dissipation films in power electronic modules to improve the cooling process and, thus, the reliability of the devices.

2. Experimental procedure

Tape-casting slurry consists of a suspension of inorganic powders in an organic solvent. The mixture contains powders (copper and diamond), dispersant agent, binder, plasticizer, and solvents. It has to be stable, homogeneous, and with a suitable viscosity according to the tape-casting process [3-4].

The starting powders are dendritic copper powder from Ecka Poudmet, Germany, and octahedral shape MBD6 diamond powders from Henan Zhongxin Co., China. Their characteristic dimensions are 30 μm length and 50 μm diameter, respectively (Table 1).

The solvent used is an azeotropic mixture of ethanol and 2-butanone (40/60). It offers a low boiling point and enables to wet both copper and diamond powders.

The binder confers its mechanical strength to the tape by forming organic bridges into the tape during solvent evaporation. PolyMethylMethAcrylate (PMMA) with a high molecular weight (120,000 – 150,000 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) and a low boiling point is used as binder in the slurry preparation.

The plasticizer enables to make the tape more flexible by decreasing the glass transition temperature of the PMMA skeleton. We use here dibutyl phthalate with a low molecular weight (300 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) as plasticizer of the PMMA.

The dispersant agent used is a phosphate ester (Cerampilot, France). It leads to a good dispersion of the powders in the slurry by developing repulsive forces between particles.

After formulation, the slurry was mixed 14 hours at 20 rpm using planetary milling. Once homogenized, the mixture is degassed 30 minutes and then directly tape casted on a Mylar silicon film using a motorized doctor blade at the desired thickness. After solvent evaporation at room temperature, the as-casted green tape exhibit good flexibility and mechanical strength, and could be cut to any desired shape. A view and a SEM micrograph of a green tape as-prepared are shown in figures 1 and 2.

The Cu/D composite tape is then heat-treated. At first, a debinding treatment of two hours at 400°C under air was carried out in order to dispose of the

organics remaining in the green tape (binder, plasticizer, dispersant). The debinding treatment leading to the oxidation of the copper powders, a reducing treatment of one hour at 400°C under Ar/H₂ has to be carried out on the tape in a second time.

An important feature of the reducing treatment is that copper nanoparticles have deposited onto diamond reinforcements under Ar/H₂. It was demonstrated that the dispersant agent used in the formulation (phosphate ester) was responsible for the deposition of these copper nanoparticles on diamonds through the creation of C-O-P-O-Cu and/or C-P-O-Cu chemical bonds during the reducing heat-treatment. Figure 3 shows an SEM micrograph of an as-treated diamond particle where Cu particles have deposited.

Therefore, the sintered Cu/D composite exhibits strong chemical bonding between the copper matrix and the diamond particles without any interlayer material such as carbide forming materials usually employed. The material thus features very weak thermal boundary resistance at the Cu/D interface, which is strongly beneficial to the thermal properties of the final material.

Following the thermal treatments, the composite are sintered by uniaxial hot pressing (induction heating) at 650°C, 50 MPa, during 30 minutes. Figures 4 and 5 shows a scheme of the hot pressing device and a photograph of a Cu/20 vol. % D composite material fabricated as-described above. Composite films of any desired thickness could be made by pressing layers of composite together.

Cu/D with diamond volume fractions of 10, 20, 30 and 40 % were fabricated. The sintered Cu/D composites were investigated from both aspects of thermal properties and microstructure. Density was measured by Archiméd's method. Composites microstructure was observed by optical and scanning electron microscopy. Thermal diffusivity and CTE were evaluated through flash laser method and dilatometry, respectively. Thermal conductivity (K_c) was calculated from thermal diffusivity (D_c) using the following relationship:

$$K_c = D_c C_{p,c} \rho_c \quad (1)$$

where $C_{p,c}$ and ρ_c are the specific heat and the density of the Cu/D composite.

3. Results

The as-fabricated Cu/D composites all exhibit densities close to the fully dense material (above 96% in relative density), which means that the Cu particles deposition process effectively enables to get cohesive interface between diamond reinforcements and copper matrix. We observe however an average compaction decrease when diamond volume fraction increases from 10 to 40 %, which is rationally explained by the fact that high reinforcements volume fractions prevent the creeping process from being optimal.

Experimental thermal conductivity values were compared to theoretical values predicted by Maxwell's model (2) (Figure 7):

$$K_c = K_m \frac{[2(\frac{K_d}{K_m} - 1)V_d + (\frac{K_d}{K_m} + 2)]}{[(1 - \frac{K_d}{K_m})V_d + (\frac{K_d}{K_m} + 2)]} \quad (2)$$

where K_m , K_d , and K_c are the thermal conductivities of the copper matrix, the diamond reinforcements, and the composite material, respectively; V_m and V_d are the volume fractions of the copper matrix and the diamond reinforcements, respectively. In agreement with theory, we observe that the TC of the composites increase with diamond volume fraction. The experimental TCs are lower than the theoretical TCs but in the same range of values. The gap between theoretical and experimental values can be explained by the existence of thermal boundary resistances at the Cu/D interface, which is not taken into account by Maxwell's model. However, the Cu/D composite films fabricated exhibit TCs ranging from 390 to 490 $W.m^{-1}.K^{-1}$ in average, and frequently reach 500 $W.m^{-1}.K^{-1}$ with diamond volume fractions of 30 and 40 %, which is a strong enhancement compared to pure copper ($TC_{Cu} = 400 W.m^{-1}.K^{-1}$).

Experimental CTEs values were compared to theoretical values calculated from Kerner's model (3) (Figure 8):

$$\alpha_c = \alpha_m V_m + \alpha_d V_d + \frac{V_d(1-V_d)(\alpha_d - \alpha_m)(E_d - E_m)}{E_m(1-V_d) + E_d V_d + (\frac{3E_d E_m}{4G_m})} \quad (3)$$

where α_m , α_d , and α_c are the CTEs of the copper matrix, the diamond reinforcements, and the composite material, respectively; V_m and V_d are the copper matrix and diamond reinforcements

respective volume fractions; E_m and E_d the bulk modulus of the copper matrix and of the diamond reinforcements, respectively; G_m the shear modulus of the copper matrix. In agreement with theory, we observe that the CTE of the composite films decrease when diamond volume fraction increases. Experimental CTEs are higher than theoretical CTEs predicted by Kerner's model. This is also to be related to the probable existence of thermal boundary resistances and porosity in the Cu/D composites. However, promising results are obtained since the CTEs range from $17.5.10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ to $12.10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ with diamond volume fraction ranging from 10 to 40 %, which represents a strong improvement compared to pure copper ($CTE_{Cu} = 17.10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$).

4. Conclusions

Diamond reinforced copper matrix composite films were fabricated by tape casting and hot pressing. Tape casting provides an efficient and repeatable solution to process Cu/D composite films with numerous advantages: low capital cost, large scale capability, good surface finish, accurate thickness control, and material net-shaping capability. Hot pressing enables the fast consolidation of Cu/D composites of any desired shape and thickness. The as-fabricated Cu/D composite films exhibit very interesting thermal properties by associating a thermal conductivity as high as $520 W.m^{-1}.K^{-1}$ to a coefficient of thermal expansion of $12.10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, which can be considered as a strong enhancement toward pure copper properties. In the end, the fabricated Cu/D composite films might be involved in the thermal management process of power electronic modules as heat-dissipation layers. The thermal performances, reliability, and lifetime of the power devices could therefore be significantly improved.

5. References

- [1] T. Schubert, A. Brendel, K. Schmid, "Interfacial design of Cu/SiC composites prepared by powder metallurgy for heat-sink applications", *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 38, pp. 2398-2403, 2007.
- [2] T. Schubert, B. Trindade, T. Weissgarber, "Interfacial design of Cu-based composite prepared by powder metallurgy for heat-sink applications", *Materials Science and Engineering A*, Vol. 475, pp. 39-44, 2008.
- [3] P.M. Geffroy, T. Chartier, J.F. Silvain, "Preparation by tape-casting and hot-pressing of copper-carbon

composite films”, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, Vol. 27, pp. 291-299, 2007.

- [4] P.M. Geffroy, T. Chartier, J.F. Silvain, “Elaboration by tape casting and hot rolling of copper/silicon carbide composite thin films for microelectronic applications”, *Material Science Forum*, Vols. 534-536, pp. 881-884, 2007.
- [5] Y. Xia, Y.Q. Song, C.G. Lin, “Effect of carbide formers on microstructure and thermal conductivity of diamond-Cu composites for heat-sinks materials”, *Trans. Nonferrous Met. Soc. China*, Vol. 19, pp. 1161-1166, 2009.
- [6] K. Chu, Z.F. Liu, C.C. Jia, “Thermal conductivity of SPS consolidated Cu/diamond composites with Cr-coated diamond particles”, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, Vol. 490, pp. 453-458, 2010.

Fig.2. SEM micrograph of a green Cu/D composite tape; dendritic copper powder and diamond particles are embedded into organics.

Table 1. Thermo-physical properties of the starting materials.

Materials	Copper	Diamond
Mean particle diameter (μm)	30	50
Density (g.cm ⁻³)	8,95	3,5
Thermal conductivity (W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)	400	1000
CTE (10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹)	17	1
Specific heat at 70°C (J.kg ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)	391,9	654,2
Bulk modulus (GPa)	130	442
Shear modulus (GPa)	48,3	-

Fig.1. View of a green copper – diamond composite tape.

Fig.3. SEM micrograph of a Cu/D composite tape after thermal treatments; copper particles have deposited onto the diamond powder embedded into the Cu matrix.

Fig.4 Scheme of the hot pressing device.

Fig.6. SEM micrograph of a Cu/20 vol. % D composite tape after hot pressing.

Fig.5. View of a dense Cu/D composite after sintering (relative density: 97 %).

Fig. 7. Thermal conductivity of the Cu/D composite films as a function of diamond volume fraction.

Fig. 8. Thermal expansion coefficient of the Cu/D composite films as a function of diamond volume fraction.